

LAKBAY-DIWA ✦
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME I ISSUE VIII

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

DECEMBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

VOLUME I | ISSUE VIII

ECHOES of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VIII (December 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

DR. JOVY DIA R. SANIEL, RN, MAN

Associate Professor IV

Biliran Province State University

School of Nursing and Health Sciences

Naval, Biliran, Philippines

[DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17838561](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17838561)

Passion in Practice

Just as the day has started,
Overwhelming need of complexity of knowledge is sorted.
Varied diseases and disorders existed,
Yielding to each intervention is twisted

Different medical-surgical nursing books are enlisted,
Intensity of comprehension is definitely obligated.
As God's creation is highly appreciated,
Strengthening nursing care is apprehended.

Associating diagnosis, laboratory findings and medications are studied,
Nursing care plans are instigated.
Instead, nursing roles are updated,
Life is precious and deserves to be respected.

Responsibility is enacted,
Never taken for granted.
Management of care is guided,
Nursing outcome is illuminated.

Phenomena in nursing health care are not to be disregarded
Despite its intricacy, responsibility is demanded.
Nightingale is forever acknowledged,
Science in nursing is to care for those in need.